

Appendix N

Sediment Core Depth Profiles

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Notes:

- Soft sediment surface
- Native sediment contact
- Native sediment inferred contact

Scale of x-axis (concentration) is linear and varies by plot, based on concentration range observed.

Total PAH and total PCB values not calculated in cases where some results were rejected.

APPENDIX N

Sediment Core Depth Profiles for Total PAHs, Total PCBs, and Lead
*Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
 Brooklyn, New York*

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